

Model-driven, logic-supported exploratory dependability analysis

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Abstract—Analyzing empirical dependability data now exceeds domain experts’ capabilities without adequate machine support. This is due to the complexity of modern IT systems, their many interdependent features, and the extensive time series involved.

This paper presents a model-driven approach to Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), which is guided by formal logic reasoning over an abstract data model. This supports domain experts in formulating and validating hypotheses, as well as guiding the exploration process.

Observations are transformed into qualitative abstractions, facilitating Answer Set Programming (ASP) based formal reasoning over system behavior and dependencies. Counterexample-guided inductive learning (CEGIL) and Rough Set Theory (RST) are used for iterative hypothesis refinement and uncertainty management.

The integrated framework enables precise, transparent, and systematic dependability assessment using commonsense engineering principles, thereby assisting analysts in the evaluation process with pertinent expert insights.

Index Terms—exploratory dependability data analysis, logic reasoning, CEGIL, rough set theory, answer set programming

I. INTRODUCTION

Empirical dependability analysis is becoming increasingly challenging due to the growing complexity of the systems under evaluation. These systems often consist of numerous components characterized by various sequential interactions and interdependencies, and they may operate across multiple operational domains. Additionally, data collection is complicated; lengthy operation sequences generate large volumes of multi-dimensional data, requiring analysis to uncover often hidden relationships among them.

As in all engineering data analysis problems, dependability [1] analysis necessitates the interpretation of the results of the mathematical analysis and derived (frequently statistical) models in the context of the engineering model of the system in a consistent way.

This interpretation necessitates simultaneous knowledge of and thinking in mathematics models, measurement setup, and the technical domain of the target system. The gradual extraction of mathematical model fragments, successively validating their credibility (to detect, for instance, measurement and data acquisition faults or incompleteness in addition to the potential

faults in the system under evaluation), and interpreting and validating them after transforming them into the engineering context increases the difficulty of the analyst’s task.

A. Exploratory Data Analysis

Exploratory data analysis (EDA) is a traditional but fundamental technique for understanding data from observations and drawing practical conclusions. Based on domain expert guidance, EDA aims to create deep models that support causal understanding beyond the description of phenomena. Unlike typical statistical or black-box ML models, our method focuses on traceable and model-based explanation. Its basic working method is the stepwise generation of *hypotheses* regarding a subset of observed features or phenomena. Subsequently, *confirmatory data analysis* (CDA) validates the hypotheses leading to a decision to discard, accept, or refine them. These elementary analysis steps are repeated until a faithful model over the validated hypotheses reaches a proper coverage of the observed phenomena.

While EDA initially relied on pure interactive visualization, modern tools support the visualization and exploration process with *built-in calculations*. These include, for example, the estimation of *approximations* (regression), the one-step determination of essential statistical characteristics (*profiling*), or the use of embedded AI and supporting tools [2] in the elementary steps.

At the same time, traditional EDA still delegates several essential steps to the expert analyst: (1) *Checking the feature and data set* to be evaluated (quality control of the instrumentation performing data collection is often looser than that of the product, making it an error source in EDA); (2) *Selection of the hypothesis-generating technique* (e.g., statistical method or visual examination); (3) *Interpretation* of the obtained result in the context of the study domain and the examined system; (4) *Generalization*, formulation of the hypothesis; (5) *Checking the consistency* of the hypothesis and previous hypotheses, as well as the physical constraints of the examined system.

In addition to the analyst’s role in hypothesis generation and interpretation, the *control of the overall EDA process* also plays a crucial part. This includes integrating the formulated hypotheses into a coherent and gradually evolving system model, as well as ensuring that the data analysis remains sufficiently comprehensive throughout the exploration.

The above process places critical demands on the analyst from many aspects. The evaluator's thoroughness is the main guarantee of a *sufficiently exhaustive analysis* of the models and the *faithfulness of the final model*. During the interpretation and evaluation process and in the control of the data analysis process, the analyst has to think *simultaneously* in the mathematical domain handling the data and the problem domain, which results in a large *abstraction gap*.

Nowadays, there are numerous AI-assisted tools [3] available to support the classical data analysis process. However, when it comes to empirical dependability analysis [4], *background knowledge* is still essential (whether related to measurement or domain-specific context) as it is crucial for formulating and validating hypotheses.

A wide range of dependability evaluation tasks are measurement-based, from validating fault tolerance (especially with fault injection) through diagnostics based on operational logs to tuning of performability and resource use. At the same time, compared to usual (e.g., business) applications, this area contains many challenges that make it difficult to perform: (1) IT systems are complex structurally in their interactions (different operating domains, asynchronous and concurrent operation); therefore, they require multidimensional and big data analysis. (2) Considering faults brings new dimensions to an already complicated task. (3) In the dependability evaluation, anomalies, and value or contextual outliers are rare events potentially causing significant hazards that must be examined with care and special techniques. (In many non-technical areas, such data are simply neglected.)

B. Related Work

Recent tools supporting EDA increasingly automate specific steps of the process. For instance, systems like Lux [2] and Zenvisage++ [5] automatically recommend visualizations based on data characteristics, accelerating early-stage pattern discovery. Similarly, AutoViz [6] streamlines the generation of statistical plots and outlier detection with minimal user input.

Some approaches incorporate analyst interaction or domain semantics to provide more targeted guidance. AIDE [7] uses active learning to identify data patterns relevant to the user, while VIADS [8] leverages medical ontologies to semantically filter large healthcare datasets. Al-Gburi et al. [9] go further by generating Jupyter notebooks for dependability analysis from ontological models of system activities, enabling structurally informed EDA trajectories.

However, these tools and methods are valuable for surface-level exploration and feature selection but lack integration with system models or formal reasoning, which limits their ability to guide structured, hypothesis-driven exploration.

In contrast, systems like CHESS-FLA [10] and logic reasoning-based reliability modeling [11] apply logic for verification purposes in dependability analysis, rather than for supporting data-oriented hypothesis-driven stepwise EDA-CDA that reduces the length of iterative loops after a hypothesis is rejected.

C. Proposed Solution

The key problem of traditional EDA is that the analyst integrates and manages multiple paradigms simultaneously. (continuous or hybrid observations, fragments of the current hypothesis and candidate and proven hypotheses from earlier ones, the system and its requirements).

- The *proposed solution* (Sec. II) integrates the entire process and the elements handled in it into the framework of *Model-Based Systems Engineering* (MBSE), the dominating method of complex system design and analysis.
- It *abstracts the observations and hypotheses* (Sec. III) into a manageable, interpretable, and explainable discrete domain. The abstraction provides logical formulas from the system and requirement model, observations, and related hypotheses. The uniform representation supports the engineering interpretation of the final results by projecting them back onto the system model (back annotation). Using the abstract form of new candidate hypotheses provided by EDA facilitates their interpretation and explanation (similar to a medical doctor saying (“You have high blood pressure and bad cholesterol values.”))
- Combining *logic reasoning and EDA* (Sec. IV) into a single framework is helpful in both directions. In *abstraction*, a subsequent logic reasoning on the abstract form of a candidate hypothesis checks its compliance with the already extracted empirical knowledge in the context of the system model. This later includes checking violations of the constraints imposed by the fault-free system. In *concretization*, the new conclusions obtained during logic reasoning represent check obligations for CDA over the detailed data. (Similarly, a medical doctor orders an illness-specific lab test after initial lab results suggest a particular illness.)
- If the formulated hypothesis turns out to be invalid, *counter-example guided hypothesis refinement* (Sec. V) can help adjust the hypothesis to obtain a more accurate understanding of the system.

Note that the proposed solution does not eliminate the need for a knowledgeable analyst but deliberates them on the most tedious tasks of generalization and interpretation. Bookkeeping in the abstract model of the already evaluated parts of the data assures the thoroughness of the evaluation process. The approach can propose or even automatically execute mathematical algorithms for the post-reasoning CDA steps in the future.

II. LOGIC REASONING-BASED EPA WORKFLOW

The logic reasoning-based data analysis *workflow* (Fig. 1) consists of (1) Hypothesis formulation, (2) Discretization, (3) Logic reasoning, (4) Evaluation, (5) Hypothesis refinement.

The first step of the process is the formulation of hypotheses using EDA (Sec. III) and statistical profiling. The analyst uses visual EDA and statistical methods (e.g., automated profiling, a rough distribution, and correlation analysis of the

Fig. 1. Logic Reasoning-based EDA Workflow

most important features) to define candidate hypotheses about system behavior. As a preparatory step, both observations and hypotheses must be *quantified* by aggregating data subsets of a similar behavior into *qualitative values* (For instance, by transforming the domain of a continuous variable into the qualitative ordinals *low, medium, high* in a similar fashion as industrial safety and security risk analysis standards do it for hazard quantification). The same quantification principle applies to the potential associations and metrics revealed by statistical profiling. For instance, association strength can be categorized as *none, probable, or certain*. In dependability analysis, special attention is also paid to indicators of outliers (*high kurtosis* in a variable, which may indicate the presence of *extreme values*).

Candidate hypotheses are developed based on qualitative values. These hypotheses will be combined with background knowledge derived from *engineering models*, such as system architectures or flow models, which outline the constraints of the solution. For example, this background knowledge may include valid value ranges, such as ensuring that time or utilization remains non-negative. This set of declarative logic statements forms the foundation of the *knowledge base*, enabling reasoning to reveal dependencies and causal relationships, such as identifying which system process leads to an extreme value.

The outcome of the reasoning can lead to two results: If a *hypothesis is validated*, its consequences can be stored in the knowledge base. In this case, a computational independent (CIM) qualitative model fragment of the system is established. If the *reasoning process reveals inconsistencies*, the user is notified and can either reject it or refine the model or the hypothesis, then re-run the reasoning process.

This later step is a typical follow-up if reasoning reveals that a particular data domain clustered into a single qualitative value is inhomogeneous and the granularity of discretization needs refinement (similarly as it is done in state partition refinement in automata synthesis). *Counterexample-Guided Inductive Synthesis/Learning* (CEGIS/L) [12] can be used

to refine the hypothesis.¹ If the validation of the original hypothesis fails because it was inconsistent with the data or the knowledge base, then an abstraction or refinement process based on CEGIL can be performed (Sec. V). This iterative process can be continued until the hypothesis becomes consistent.

By supporting model-based hypothesis generation and refinement, projecting the analysis results back onto the model enables the examination of whether the requirements associated with the model elements are being fulfilled. This allows for the identification, directly within the model, of the points in the system that need to be adjusted (e.g., in case of an overload, introducing mitigation measures or scaling resources).

III. QUALITATIVE EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

To enable discrete logic reasoning in the workflow, it is necessary to discretize the observations. The goal of qualitative EDA is to formulate the hypothesis in a discrete manner. This is preceded by the discretization of the observations and the mathematical models fitted to them.

EDA aims to formulate hypotheses based on observations that can later be tested and validated. EDA can involve *visual data exploration*, where various plots (e.g., boxplots, scatter plots, or parallel coordinates) can help reveal patterns. For example, a boxplot can indicate the presence of outliers; a scatter plot can help identify operational domains or clusters; and a parallel coordinates plot can visually highlight relationships between variables.

Statistical techniques can complement visual methods and allow for the characterization of individual variables and their relationships using statistical metrics (e.g., deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and correlation coefficients).

A. Qualitative Abstraction Techniques

Continuous variable values can be grouped through discretization into qualitative operational domains (e.g., *low, medium, and high* CPU usage). Operational domains

¹While commonly called CEGIS, we use ‘CEGIL’ (Learning) to emphasize its role in hypothesis refinement rather than program synthesis.

can be defined empirically using methods like clustering or thresholds or with the help of domain-specific knowledge.

Statistical characteristics can also be abstracted and discretized. For example, if a strong correlation exists between two variables or if a variable includes extreme values. Pre-defined thresholds can help determine what constitutes a strong correlation or an outlier in a given context.

When quantizing statistical values, threshold-based partitioning can be extended with an uncertainty region (e.g., correlations below 0.3 are definitely *rejected*, those above 0.9 are *accepted*, and values in between can be treated as *uncertain*). This approach, combined with Rough Set Theory (RST) [13] (see Sec. V), facilitates handling uncertainty and checking consistency with both the data and the background knowledge (the logic reasoning method applied supports the handling of non-determinism).

Clustering in qualitative modeling [14] is a key technique for reducing the complexity of data analysis by grouping elements that describe similar characteristics or behaviors. Let $X = \{x\}$ denote the domain of the feature to be clustered, and let $Q = \{q\} \subset \mathbb{Z}$ represent its corresponding *qualitative domain*.

As an initial step, we define non-empty subsets X_i and X_j of X such that $X_i \cap X_j = \emptyset$ and $X_i, X_j \neq \emptyset$. These subsets group together elements that display *similar behavior*, so they differ only in ways considered irrelevant for the modeling task. The notion of relevance is determined by the specific question the qualitative model aims to address.

Let $cf : X \mapsto Q$ be a *clustering function* that maps each subset X_i to a *qualitative value* q , so that $cf(X_i) = q$.

Clustering continuous values is a method used to partition a continuous feature domain into intervals that represent similar behaviors in a system. Let $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be the domain of a continuous feature and $I = I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n \subset \mathbb{R}$ real intervals [15]. These intervals represent *partitions* of the feature domain:

$$\forall I_i, I_j : I_i \cap I_j = \emptyset; \bigcup_i I_i = X \quad (1)$$

There's an *interval membership function* that simply assigns each number to an interval.

In this case, the a clustering function assigns a qualitative value to an element, the value corresponding to a one-on-one mapping with an interval partition of the feature domain.

A *qualitative landmark* [14] of two qualitative values refers to the boundary value between the two corresponding neighboring interval partitions.

B. Hypothesis Formulation

Hypotheses are expressed in discrete logic form to enable formal reasoning about system behaviors. Common hypothesis types include:

- *Cluster-based patterns*: Identified behavior clusters (e.g., medium load, low latency) can denote system states.

$$Cluster_X \rightarrow System(Stable) \quad (2)$$

- *Combined value conditions*: Certain system states emerge only from specific variable combinations (e.g., high voltage and high temperature lead to high response time).

$$Voltage(High) \cap Temperature(High) \rightarrow ResponseTime(High) \quad (3)$$

- *Causal chains*: Failure events can trigger cascading effects (e.g., fan failure leads to shutdown).

$$Failure(Fan) \rightarrow System(Overheat) \rightarrow System(ShutDown) \quad (4)$$

- *Statistical associations*: Strong correlations (e.g., high CPU and increasing I/O usage) suggest fault likelihood.

$$CPU(High) \cap IO(Increasing) \rightarrow FaultRate(Increasing) \quad (5)$$

- *Rare critical events*: Infrequent but impactful cases (e.g., very low current with system running may indicate hidden faults).

$$Current(VeryLow) \cap System(Running) \rightarrow PotentialHiddenFault \quad (6)$$

IV. VALIDATION BY LOGIC REASONING

While EDA focuses on uncovering patterns and forming hypotheses, it is equally important to validate these findings in a systematic manner. Logic reasoning provides a *formal* approach to assess the validity of the hypotheses in the context of the system under evaluation. By leveraging formal logic, analysts can go beyond statistical correlations to ensure that the derived conclusions are not only data-driven but also conceptually and structurally sound.

A. Reasoning Engine

We use *Answer Set Programming* (ASP) [16], a declarative logic programming paradigm well-suited for knowledge representation and non-monotonic reasoning. It handles defaults and uncertainties well. ASP, as a *uniformization* paradigm for knowledge of different sources, enables the formalization of hypotheses, domain knowledge, and system constraints as logic rules and facts. It allows the checking of consistency between hypotheses, observations and background knowledge.

The nonmonotonic reasoning of ASP is well-suited to track changes occurring during the MBSE process, as the inference can be rerun in a modular way with the changes. Previous hypotheses can be re-evaluated under the altered circumstances.

The result of an ASP program is called *answer sets* (following the stable model semantics [17]), which is a consistent set of literals that represent the entire solution space that satisfies all rules and constraints of the program. $AS(P)$ is the operator that, given a logic program P , defines the procedure for computing all of its answer sets. ASP programs can be solved by ASP solvers, a widely used solver is Clingo [18], which combines a high-performance grounder and solver and supports features such as optimization, constraints, and

external function integration. Clingo also provides a Python API, enabling seamless integration with external systems to perform data analysis tasks, e.g., in Jupyter.

B. Input Models

Engineering input models are *structured system models* that describe the system architecture, the dependencies between components, data flows, and even state machines that describe system behavior. These models provide a contextual understanding of how the system operates and form the structural basis for logic reasoning.

The solution is based on an *MBSE-based model management solution* where the goal is to manage models from different sources in a single representation.

Besides the system model, the rule base serves as the semantic layer of the reasoning process. This rule base may include two major types of knowledge: (1) general-purpose reasoning rules and (2) domain-specific rules.

General-purpose rules are logic-based constructs that are domain-independent. These often include transitive dependency rules, consistency constraints, or default behavior assumptions. For example, if component A depends on component B , and component B on component C , then one may infer that A transitively depends on C .

Domain-specific rules encode expert knowledge or already validated hypotheses. These rules may also embed implicit assumptions that are well-understood by practitioners but not explicitly stated in system documentation.

C. Evaluation of the Results

The ASP reasoning engine can apply different reasoning modes: (1) It can return a single valid solution; (2) It can enumerate all possible solutions; (3) It also supports optimization, where solutions are ranked based on weights and priorities.

During the reasoning process, we first construct the ASP program P , which consists of (Eq. 7): (1) Qualitative observations; (2) Background knowledge (rules and dependencies); (3) The hypothesis to be evaluated (represented as a logic formulae).

$$P = \{Observation \cup Rules \cup Hypothesis\} \quad (7)$$

The abstraction process creates a *Galois connection* between the concrete data and their qualitative representation. This assures that if a fact holds in the original concrete model, it will also hold true in the abstract logical space, thus *preserving all-important engineering properties* under abstraction. However, due to the nature of abstraction, there may be multiple *spurious solutions* that are non-existent in the concrete data when solving the ASP program.

Solving the ASP program can have two type of outcomes:

- If the ASP program is *satisfiable*, then the hypothesis is valid. It means that it can be deduced from the available rules, observations, and background knowledge. The resulting knowledge can be saved to the knowledge base as a confirmed rule.

- If the ASP program is *unsatisfiable*, then the hypothesis is invalid under the current assumptions. This could indicate that (1) There are conflicting facts in the knowledge base or the data; (2) Constraints are violated.

The analyst can systematically refine the underlying model when the reasoning process leads to inconsistency. One way is the abstraction or refinement applied to the observations. In this case, the abstraction may need to be fine-tuned by adjusting the qualitative landmarks of the model.

Logic reasoning frameworks are only as powerful as the rules and facts they encode. A valid hypothesis may appear unsupported if relevant observations or domain-specific rules are missing. To address this issue, the analyst may need to extend the background knowledge, introduce new features (e.g., memory utilization, network congestion), and encode additional domain rules.

Re-evaluating the hypothesis may involve refining it to better align with observations. This step is not a failure of the reasoning process but rather a core aspect of its epistemological robustness. The model and hypothesis refinement process is inherently iterative, supporting *incremental knowledge building through logic reasoning*.

V. HYPOTHESIS REFINEMENT WITH CEGIL

When the hypothesis cannot be validated at first, it may need to be refined. CEGIL is an iterative process that starts from an initial hypothesis and, using *positive and negative examples*, abstracts or refines the hypothesis. In the case of a positive example, it generalizes the hypothesis (it expands the range of cases covered). In the case of a negative example (counterexample), it restricts the hypothesis (it narrows the range of cases covered). This way, negative examples gradually eliminate overly general hypotheses, while positive examples eliminate overly specific ones. As a result, the hypothesis space converges meaning that the refined hypothesis covers all positive examples and none of the negative ones.

Formally, if P denotes the set of positive examples and N the set of negative examples, then a hypothesis h is consistent with the examples if h is true (satisfied) for every $p \in P$, and false for every $n \in N$. The hypothesis space $H_{P,N}$ is then the set of all hypotheses h that are consistent with both P and N .

This CEGIL-based iterative abstraction and refinement process can be carried out using Rough Set Theory (RST) [19], which provides a formal framework for handling uncertain or incomplete knowledge.

RST is based on the concept [20], [21] of an approximation space, which consists of a universe U (the set of all objects/observations) and an indiscernibility relation $R \subseteq U \times U$.

RST defines *information system* as a pair $IS = (U, A)$, where U is a non-empty finite set of objects called the *universe* and A is a non-empty finite set of *attributes* such that: $a : U \rightarrow V_a$ for every $a \in A$. The set V_a is called *value set* of a .

R is an equivalence relation that expresses which objects are indiscernible to the system based on the available attributes. The *equivalence class* of an object $x \in U$ contains all the objects from them x is indiscernible. It is denoted by $[x]_R$.

The equivalence classes defined by R are called approximation sets. For an arbitrary target set $X \subseteq U$. In the context of the hypothesis validation, the target set includes the observations covered by a hypothesis. RST defines two main approximations: the lower approximation (\underline{X}) (Equation 8) and the upper approximation (\overline{X}) (Equation 9).

$$\underline{X} = \{x \in U \mid [x]_R \subseteq X\} \quad (8)$$

$$\overline{X} = \{x \in U \mid [x]_R \cap X \neq \emptyset\} \quad (9)$$

The approximations partition the universe of the objects into three disjoint regions according to the decidability of containment in X :

$$POS(X) = \underline{B}(X), \text{ the positive region} \quad (10)$$

$$BND(X) = \overline{B}(X) - \underline{B}(X), \text{ the boundary region} \quad (11)$$

$$NEG(X) = U - \overline{B}(X), \text{ the negative region} \quad (12)$$

- If an object $x \in POS(X)$, then it certainly belongs to target set X
- If an object $x \in BND(X)$, then it is undecidable whether the object x belongs to target set X or not.
- If an object $x \in NEG(X)$, then it certainly doesn't belong to target set X .

By appropriately selecting the indiscernibility relation, the approximation can be relaxed [22], allowing RST to handle the contradictions that frequently occur in real-world data. From a practical perspective, dealing with conflicting data, RST handles the contradicting observations that falls into the boundary region, thereby providing guidance for resolving the conflict (e.g., introducing additional attributes or refining the data granularity).

The process defined by CEGIL can be described using RST. The lower approximation of the set P (the positive examples) represents the region that, based on attributes, can be definitively assigned to the hypothesis, while the upper approximation represents the region that could possibly belong to the concept.

The domain H^+ judged as positive by the hypothesis can be considered a candidate upper approximation of the target concept, while the set of elements that the hypothesis deems definitely positive forms the candidate lower approximation.

During the CEGIL process, when a negative counterexample $n \in N$ is identified, it indicates that n was mistakenly included in the positive region of the hypothesis ($n \in H^+$, even though $n \notin P$). In rough set terms, this means that an element from N has entered the current upper approximation of P : that is, there exists an equivalence class $[n]_R$ such that $[n]_R \cap P \neq \emptyset$ and $[n]_R \cap N \neq \emptyset$. Such classes are responsible for the boundary region of the concept (its uncertainty).

The negative counterexample forces a refinement of the hypothesis by narrowing its upper approximation: the hypothesis must be adjusted so that n no longer belongs to H^+ . Accordingly, the upper approximation is reduced by excluding those elementary sets that contain objects similar to n .

Similarly, if a positive example $p \in P$ is left out of the hypothesis coverage ($p \notin H^+$, even though $p \in P$), then the hypothesis needs to be generalized so that p is included in the positive region. This leads to an expansion of H^+ (the upper approximation), and potentially an increase in the lower approximation as well.

In this way, the steps of CEGIL correspond to the refinement of the lower and upper approximations until the sets of positive and negative examples become separated. That is, we reach a point where $\underline{P} = \overline{P}$ for the learned concept, meaning the concept can be precisely described with no boundary region.

If this cannot be achieved with the current set of attributes, the remaining uncertainty in the boundary region shows where contradictions persist, that is, which combinations of objects belong to equivalence classes that intersect both P and N . This provides direct guidance on how the hypothesis should be enriched, for example by introducing a new attribute to resolve the conflict.

VI. EXAMPLE

The following example illustrates the individual steps of the workflow. Starting from observational data, we formulate a hypothesis. The data is discretized, and a formal rule is derived from the hypothesis. Using background knowledge, we perform logic reasoning with ASP and evaluate the results.

In the system under evaluation, we measured CPU load (%) and system response time (ms). During visual analysis, a relationship was observed between CPU load and response time. This was confirmed by statistical evaluation: the Pearson correlation coefficient between the two variables was 0.7, indicating a strong positive relationship.

We model the system context using ArchiMate (Fig. ??). The monitored system includes a Node representing the server infrastructure (including the CPU), an Application Service responsible for the order service, and a Business Process capturing the user operation: order handling. These elements are linked via serves relationships, enabling traceability from infrastructure states to business outcomes.

Based on the visual analysis and statistical relationships (e.g., Fig. 2), the following abstractions can be made:

- CPU Usage: 0-60%: Low; 60-90%: Medium; 90-100%: High
- Response Time: 0-145ms: Acceptable; 145-225ms: Degraded; >225ms: Critical

The correlation value of 0.7 between CPU and Response Time falls into the *Strong* category, as in most statistical interpretations, a correlation of 0.7 is usually considered strong: $Correlation(CPU, ResponseTime, Strong)$

A hypothesis (Eq. 13) can be formulated during the EDA process: "If the CPU load reaches the *High* level, then the response time is also *High* (Degraded or Critical)."

$$CPU(High) \rightarrow ResponseTime \in \{Degraded, Critical\} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 2. Boxplot of CPU Usage and Response Time

The rules in the background knowledge can describe general principles about the system. In the example, the two rules we used are:

- Rule 14: If CPU utilization is high, then there is Resource Contention.
- Rule 15: If there is Resource Contention, then the response time falls into a higher category.

$$CPU(High) \rightarrow ResourceContention \quad (14)$$

$$ResourceContention \rightarrow ResponseTime \in \{Degraded, Critical\} \quad (15)$$

With reasoning with ASP, we determine the stable model of the observations, rules, and the hypothesis.

If the reasoning does not lead to a contradiction it can be stated that the hypothesis is valid. As reasoning supports the hypothesis, hypothesis can be accepted and it can be stored in the knowledge base as a rule. The resulting qualitative rule may become part of a reliability model and can be used for dimensioning (e.g., setting the CPU design threshold slightly lower than the *High* value at 85%).

During the evaluation of the results *inconsistencies may emerge* between the hypothesis and the data. For example, in some cases, high CPU usage may not appear with high response times, suggesting that other factors may also influence the outcome. In this case, the analyst may revisit the results, refine the discretization process, or enrich the background models with new information (e.g., introducing rules related to memory usage). Conflict resolution can be supported by using RST, which helps manage uncertainty arising from abstraction and guides the refinement process.

A. Hypothesis Refinement

In the discrete dataset, we can find cases (Fig. 3) where CPU load is high, yet the response time did not increase significantly (e.g., it remained within the normal range). Counterexamples are measurements where $CPU = 85\%$ (High category), but $ResponseTime$ is in the *Normal* range. This contradicts our initial hypothesis (Eq. 13), since the premise is satisfied, but the conclusion is not. It suggests that high CPU usage alone is not a sufficient condition for high response time, other resources or factors are involved.

Using approximation-based refinement in RST, the original hypothesis could be refined. The lower and upper approximations, updated based on positive and negative examples,

Fig. 3. Reasoning environment indicating negative examples

would support the iterative refinement of the hypothesis until it becomes fully consistent with the observations.

In such cases, we observe that the set of observations covered by the original hypothesis yields mixed decision outcomes. In some instances, the $ResponseTime$ is *High* (Degraded/Critical), while in others it is not. So far, only CPU load has been considered among the attributes in the information system (let this be $A = \{CPU\}$), and based on this, the $CPU = High$ equivalence class intersects both the cases with high response time and those within the normal range. In terms of the decision attribute $ResponseTime$, this represents a conflict, as the equivalence class contains both positive and negative outcomes.

To resolve the conflict, we need to examine which additional attribute could distinguish between the cases where CPU usage is high but the response time does not degrade. Based on expert knowledge, it is suspected that other resources (e.g., memory, network) may influence this relationship.

The memory utilization is available in the data, and the expert decides to incorporate it into the hypothesis. This way they can add the memory to the hypothesis (Eq. 16): "If the CPU load reaches the *High* level and the memory usage is also *High*, then the response time is also *High* (Degraded or Critical)."

$$CPU(High) \cap Memory(High) \rightarrow ResponseTime \in \{Degraded, Critical\} \quad (16)$$

This effectively refines the original hypothesis by adding an additional condition. Now, the attribute set becomes $A' = \{CPU, Memory\}$, containing two features. In this case, the new hypothesis becomes consistent with all observed instances: whenever both resources are saturated, a slowdown always occurs; when only CPU is saturated but memory is not, slowdown does not necessarily follow, and the hypothesis makes no claim in such cases, so it remains valid. The validity of the refined hypothesis are verified with logic reasoning. This can confirm that, when combined with the observations and background knowledge, the new hypothesis does not lead to contradiction, meaning it is valid.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposes a solution that EDA with formal logic reasoning into MBSE to enhance the analysis of dependable systems. This approach allows for well-structured and explainable reasoning about observations and system models by abstracting complex data into qualitative values and representing hypotheses as logical formulas. ASP facilitates automated validation, while iterative refinement through CEGIL and RST ensures consistency. Additionally, the technique accommodates different levels of data quantification and hierarchical refinement. The experimental framework is in the form of a Jupyter notebook and dashboard (Fig. 3), relying on the rich support of methods.

A. Future Work

The principles presented in the paper are the results of several industrial projects with the logic layer as a thinking pattern. However, two main pain points remain unsolved:

(1) *Support for Effective Process Organization*: The global planning of an effective process from the individual steps remains an obligation of the analysts. Here, adaptation of the concepts of integrated diagnostics [23] proven by decades-long practical use is our main research direction.

(2) *Skills in statistics*: Another key challenge is bridging the gap between qualitative, abstract reasoning and the concrete data checks required by CDA, which still demand strong statistical and analytical skills. Here, future support aims at a knowledge base summarizing the relevant statistical methods, application preconditions, and their implementation. In the long term, this promises that the high-level reasoning environment automatically "calls out" to the data analysis layer, the knowledge base estimates a CDA-based check, executes the method, and returns the result.

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